

CODEN [USA]: IAJPB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**HOW AND WHAT TYPE OF RESEARCH CAN EFFECTIVELY
ARREST ALL FORM OF TUBERCULOSIS ESPECIALLY
LATENT INFECTIOUS TUBERCULOSIS**¹Dr. Manal Tanveer, ²Dr. Anjum Hameed, ³Dr. Zermina Azhar¹House Officer, Jinnah Hospital Lahore, ²MALC, Regional Coordinator- Gilgit-Baltistan, ³House Officer Gynae Unit 2 Jinnah Hospital Lahore.

Article Received: March 2019

Accepted: April 2019

Published: May 2019

Abstract:

The primary objective of this research was to provide advocacy and leadership to use more resources for the global TB control program along with the provision of fund receiving forums and TB research implementation. Tuberculosis (TB) causes millions of deaths every year across the globe and it is ranked among most alarming infectious diseases. This research overviews general treatment guidelines, diagnosis and pathogenesis of TB. Before commencement of this review, we explored related articles on PubMed; in addition to that, we also searched international institutes official pages on the web such as WHO for related clinical guidelines and reports. The objective of this research paper is to spread general awareness among healthcare professionals in order to educate them along with the education of public, patients and policy makers.

It also aimed to ensure outcomes through identified opportunities and fill the gaps. The movement against TB is a partnership and collaborative effort to arrest TB. This movement operates under the guidelines of WHO and research related protocols. There were two major components of research-oriented movement consisting of global TB research analysis and development of research roadmap to arrest TB. Many others also became the part of this campaign including research, scientists, development, operational and applied research with agencies and stakeholders.

Keywords: All Form Of Tuberculosis, Specially, Latent Infectious Tuberculosis, Effectively, Arrest.

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Please cite this article in press Manal Tanveer et al., *How and What Type of Research Can Effectively Arrest All Form of Tuberculosis Especially Latent Infectious Tuberculosis.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(05).

INTRODUCTION:

Tuberculosis is an unacceptable burden with its increased disease burden and mortality rate [1]. Its diagnostic tools are not that much effective which tend to use older technology for the measurement of disease burden. Sputum microscopy is an older type of Tuberculosis diagnostic tools which required proper supervision, adherence and treatment such as Tuberculosis vaccines and drugs. Better Tuberculosis controls required new diagnostic and treatment options [2]. Research work performs a key role in the achievement of health goals. The research aims to decrease the levels of deaths due to TB than previous levels of 1990 [3]. Since 2004, the rate of TB is falling at a rate of one percent annually [1]. Realistic goal achievement depends on TB control technological revolution. Basic implementation and accelerated

goals achievement are possible through increased research work [4]. To recognize this need, accelerated research work is required to arrest TB in order to achieve international goals [5, 6].

RESULT:

It includes various questions such as “Who is funding? How much is funding? and What is being funded?”. Various elements and questions were brought together for research and development [7]. The estimate of the revised Global TB stop plan was US\$ 9.8 Billion back in 2011 – 2015 which required fifty percent in the prevalence of TB which was least required [8]. This plan included target investments for operational and fundamental research for new vaccines, diagnostics and drugs.

Table – I: Funding Details

Component	Funding US\$ Billion	Percentage
Implementation	36.9	79
DOTS	22.6	48
Drug-resistant TB	7.1	15
TB/HIV	2.8	6
Laboratory Strengthening	4	8
Technical Assistance	0.4	1
Research and Development	9.8	21
Fundamental Research	2.1	5
New Diagnostics	1.7	4
New Drugs	3.7	8
New Vaccines	1.9	4
Operational Research	0.4	1
All Components	46.7	100

Research and development funding details are as under with respect to the funding level of 2009 – 2010 and domestic funding.

Table – II: Research and Development

Research and Development	Funding (2009-2010) Level	Domestic Funding
Required Funding	37	37
Available Funding	21	23
Selected Countries	15	17
Rest of the World	5	6
External Donor	3	3
Funding Gap	13	11
Funding Required	10	10
Funding Available 2009	3	3
Funding Gap (E-F)	6	6
Total Funding Gap	19	17

Global TB research and development plan span over a variety of topic, which is as under:

Table – III: Topic Details

Topic	Number
Drug Use and Development	28
Chemoprophylaxis Effectiveness	9
Optimal Drug Treatment Duration	9
New Anti-TB Drug Development	7
Standard Pharmacokinetics Drugs	7
Drug Interaction	7
Second Line Drugs Pharmacokinetics	7
Diagnostic and Diagnosis Test	27
Active TB Novel Diagnostic	14
Methods for Drug Sensitivity Test	11
Active TB Diagnostic Evaluation	8
Successful Treatment Biomarkers	8
Public Health and Epidemiology	20
Global TB Burden Measurement	8
Community Role in TB Determination	5
Literacy Programs Effect	5
Health Services Research	16

Diagnostic Delay Causes	4
TB Related Costs	4
Case Finding Role	4
Integration of HIV and TB Services	4
Staff Training	4
Basic Scientific Research	13
TB Protection Identification	4
Latency Understanding	4
Understanding Phenotypic and Genetic Markers	4
Animal Model Development	4
Vaccine Development	13
New TB Vaccine Trials	8

TB research Agendas:

In the past ten years, various groups have posed different research agendas. We also carried out a systematic review for TB research agendas for the evaluation of main research themes and questions. We need to assess priorities and methods to identify emerging messages [9]. Various articles and papers were shortlisted for review which was on different topics with a broader perspective. Questions mainly focused on prevention, treatment of MDR-TB and TB/HIV co-infection. These questions also reflected the inefficiencies of short-course chemotherapy limitations and sputum smear microscopy. There is a vibrant need for health system and epidemiology research for effective TB control. Most of the investigations are affected by less priority given to basic research. Great variations are found in the identification priorities and methods. Counselling and

expert opinion also provide objective measurable criteria and priorities of the research. Importance of research questions is greatly helpful for the systemic review of the reproducible criteria.

Key Research Questions:

There were four workshops conducted in 2009 – 10 which laid the roadmap in order to identify priorities and gaps for the continuous research process. Workshops included different discussions on various topics such as vaccines, drugs and diagnostics. A number of scientists, civil society, program managers, members and donors attended the workshop. The objectives of this workshop were a review of research activities, new diagnostics, vaccines and drug development. Science primarily intervened the improvement of TB control innovative programs [10].

The workshop conducted in 2010 was to fight against Tuberculosis, AIDS and Malaria through pragmatic and operational research to control and care TB. These workshops identified five major areas of screening & diagnosis access, sustainable collaborative development to arrest TB, treatment & prevention of TB among HIV patients, optimal delivery and access to delivery and capacity building. Various questions were developed by the participants with different suggestions and comments to arrest TB [11, 12].

Prioritization of research questions:

About 250 research-based questions were raised in the workshops in different areas which include basic science, research and development of vaccines, drugs and diagnostics, public health and operational research. These questions were classified through objectivity and measurable indicators such as child health and nutritional state [13]. Prioritization was also dependent on the ultimate utilization of tools to counter mortality and morbidity due to TB. Priority ranking process included wide research areas, clinical care, public health and managerial aspects.

International TB elimination research roadmap:

Better TB control is possible through addressing key questions about TB research program in a specified timeline as prescribed by the experts to handle feasibility and knowledge gaps. A common framework is possible through the collaborative effort for TB control along with the promotion of TB research especially in the countries with higher burdens of TB. Various international forums have also discussed key scientific ideas among NGOs and stakeholders with the support of World TB investors. The objective of this meeting was to discuss the roadmap of global, synergetic and harmonized TB research with coordinated funding. It was conclusively agreed to speed up the research and coordination process of TB research.

DISCUSSION:

TB research response is pressing issue all over the world for human and health development with accelerated TB control progress. TB control affects the direct impact on the reduction of TB burden and also saves lives; moreover, it also helps to control poverty and promotes economic and social progression. New tools have been introduced in the last decade after years of neglect. At present TB control is better than ever as breakthroughs have been achieved and much more is in pipeline. Latest breakthroughs include MTB/RIF which is capable to diagnose TB and rifampicin in a time of one hundred minutes [14].

More trials on Phase I & II are also in the pipeline of pre-clinical and clinical research [15].

Ten vaccines are in the clinical evaluation process among which four are in Phase-II [16]. Most of the funds are raised through a public-private partnership which is very much helpful for the ongoing research and development process. The combined effort is mandatory to arrest TB in an effective way by 2050 along with the implementation of new diagnostic and treatment strategies including drug-resistant TB, drug susceptible TB, overt TB short treatment and massive vaccination campaigns [17]. More work is required to develop diagnostic and treatment approaches for all types of TB which also includes latent Tuberculosis infection [18].

Potential risk groups need special focus as until the development of phase the combinational treatment may be optimal for such cases [19]. There is a higher attrition rate of development pathway with success chances of the emerging products especially for new products [20]. Research also requires reinforced health control to counter endemic countries through innovative processes [21]. WHO endorses newly introduced tools through recommended technical support and policies in vogue especially for the molecular diagnostics and also strives for the availability of the latest developed tools [20]. Rapid transfer of newly emerged products is only possible through global coordination especially in the endemic countries. Still primary and major challenges need attention. Intake of donors and rationalized used of funds for research and development purposes is also necessary. Highly affected regions can also play their role in this process through health seminars and workshops with shared objectives and roadmaps [22, 23].

CONCLUSION:

More discussion forums will build even stronger consensus and harmonized global TB control research programs in the coming years through practice and policy. It is a cross-disciplinary coordinated effort which addresses and identified strategic concrete public health results. International TB research and development program to arrest TB will act as a concrete framework to synergize all the efforts made for TB control through research efforts all over the world. Research movement can crucially handle the existing resources and it can also accelerate much required TB research programs in order to achieve internationally set targets.

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